

ISSUES OF CREATIVE STUDY OF THE EXPERIENCE OF EUROPEAN COUNTRIES IMPLEMENTATION OF STEAM -METHODOLOGY IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract The article deals with the necessity of implementing STEAM-education in preschool sphere. In this regard, STEAM-education has been widely introduced into the system of preschool education in many countries of the world, which are intensively developing and introducing high technologies. In Uzbekistan it is necessary to critically and creatively study foreign experience of STEAM-education introduction in preschool sphere, training and professional development of personnel for these purposes.

Key words: STEM, STEAM, digitalization of society, necessity of critical and creative study of foreign experience of STEAM-education implementation, development of professional competence of preschool teacher.

Аннотация В статье изучаются вопросы необходимости внедрения STEAM-образования в дошкольную сферу. Во многих странах мира, интенсивно развивающих и внедряющих высокие технологии, в последнее время в систему дошкольного образования широко внедряется STEAM-образование. В Узбекистане необходимо критически и творчески изучить зарубежный опыт внедрения STEAM-образования в дошкольную сферу, подготовки и повышения квалификации кадров для этих целей.

Ключевые слова: STEM, STEAM, цифровизация общества, необходимость критического и творческого изучения зарубежного опыта внедрения STEAM-образования, развитие профессиональной компетентности педагога дошкольного образования

Sustainable development of the state in the conditions of globalization, development of digital technologies is associated with the possibility of obtaining knowledge throughout life, an important period of which is preschool education. Currently, the educational technologies used in the preschool education system do not meet the challenges of a rapidly changing society, the intensive development of computer technology and the Internet, which fundamentally change life at all levels of its existence. This circumstance requires new approaches to the development of intellectual, creative abilities and personal qualities of children who will have to live in an even more technologized and digitalized world. According to the main theoretical and practical methodologists in the European STEAM-Educational Technology Centers Kristof Fenivesi (Finnish Institute for Educational Research, University of Jyväskylä, Finland), Janika Leoste, Maira Tuul, Tiia Hyun (School of Educational Sciences, Tallinn University, Estonia), Zsolt Lavichsa, (Linz School of Education, Johannes Kepler University, Linz, Austria) - "the development of STEAM pedagogical methodologies for the development of skills, in particular creativity and critical thinking, are increasingly identified as necessary components of future education. Critical thinking of students and teachers as well as pedagogical methods can go beyond academic disciplines and are also central to sustainable education [1]

UNICEF's global report on early childhood education, A World Ready to Learn: Prioritizing Quality Early Childhood Education [2] notes that successful early childhood education is a critical component of the future of education reduces the risk of socio-economic problems such as unemployment, extremism, declining state economic performance, etc. This indicates that children who have attended preschool for at least one year are more likely to acquire the life skills necessary for success in school, are less likely to repeat or drop out of school, and have more opportunities to contribute to society. As a result, this area of education is a priority for many modern nations. We join a group of authors from the United States, Australia, Austria, Finland and Spain in stating that "the development of

STEAM pedagogies to develop skills, particularly creativity and critical thinking, are increasingly identified as necessary components of future education. Critical thinking by students and teachers, as well as pedagogical methods, can go beyond academic disciplines and are also central to sustainable education." [3] STEM (an acronym for the English words: Science (S), Technology (T), Engineering (E) and Math (M)) is understood as a combination of science (in the sense of natural science), technology, engineering and math, and STEM education is the foundation for training workers in high technology. It involves both acquiring knowledge in these sciences and the ability to apply them in practice.

The STEAM platform not only teaches students to not only think critically, solve problems, and use creativity, but also prepares them for jobs in growth-oriented fields. The U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics report projects a 10.8% growth in STEM and STEAM occupations between c 2022-2032, compared to 2.3% for non-STEM occupations. It also cites average annual wages for STEM/STEAM occupations at \$97,980, compared to \$44,670 for all occupations [4]. we can conclude that the task of educational systems is to prepare young people for the requirements of the modern labor market, including providing them with adequate digital skills - this issue has been discussed for several decades.

The integration of the principles of natural sciences, technology, engineering, art and mathematics (STEAM) into regular curricula is proposed as an effective solution to increase students' interest in professions that require good digital skills (i.e., most professions in the coming decades).

In the near future, at least 90% of professional roles in Europe will require basic digital skills similar to basic literacy or numeracy skills. However, improvements in this area are slow. The situation is aggravated by the fact that 88% of workplaces do nothing to improve the digital skills of their employees, often citing high costs as the main obstacle to taking measures to address the lack of digital skills. Combined with the EU's ambitious goal of ensuring that at least 80% of the adult population has basic digital skills by 2030, it becomes obvious

that, together with other participants, the educational systems of EU countries should contribute to achieving this goal.

Since the development of technology requires the training of professional personnel related to computer science and engineering, STEM centers are being specially created in different countries (Finland, Estonia, Hungary, Austria, Spain, USA, Australia), which are designed to become a motivational platform for young people to choose a future profession in the field of computer technology, demonstrating the prospect of their development in the future. It should be noted that along with the development of science and technology, creative industries are also developing. In this regard, creative, artistic disciplines included in the concept of Arts are actively included in STEM education. This is due to the fact that innovative solutions require a high level of creativity, non-standard thinking, and original approaches that can be provided within the framework of Arts education. Thus, there is an active transition from STEM to STEAM education (the additional letter "A" stands for art). While these initiatives are a great start to explore the four areas of knowledge, they lack such an important process as creativity and innovation. Students enrolled in STEM programs may have more opportunities for hands-on learning, but they are limited to science, technology, engineering and mathematics. Modern economics requires much more than understanding only these areas - it requires application, creativity. Why we need both natural sciences and humanities for education in the conditions of the Fourth Industrial Revolution?

A group of authors specializing in the STEAM method of appeal (Fenyvesi, K., Brownell, C., Pekonen, O., Lavicza, Z., & Somlyódy, N), highlighting those components that focus on "mathematical arts and creativity", combining these various educational cultures with a more global perspective, believe that "Development abilities for joint and inter-, multi- and trans-disciplinary problem solving, allowing students to discover unexpected connections between various aspects of various complex phenomena, is not only a useful tool, but is also recognized as one of the most important goals of modern learning societies.

STEAM in modern European schools is a dynamically developing, but still little-explored area[5] The authors cite three examples from research projects (for example, "Da Vinci Machines" and 3D printing, " Flipped" learning and augmented reality applications), which demonstrate a situation where pedagogical practice using a new technology, it was undergoing research on implementation and needed a significant revision already in connection with the development of technology until the publication of the study and claim , that research methodologies should be adapted to meet rapidly changing technologies.[5]

Research by Graham Nicholas, James Brouillette shows that STEAM is a promising approach that allows you to positively influence student academic performance and the effectiveness of teachers. In a 2016 study, scientists studied the impact of STEAM lessons on the study of physics in grades 3-5 of an elementary school in an urban district with a high level of poverty. The results showed that students who received only nine hours of STEAM lessons achieved improved academic performance in natural sciences [6].

Other research - authors - Marisol Cunnington, Andrea Kantrowitz, Susanne Harnett, and Aline Hill-Ries., conducted in 2014, shows that the combination of STEAM and literacy can positively affect cognitive development, improve literacy and mathematical skills, and help students to think meaningfully about their work and their activities Development of pedagogical methods for skills development in particular, creative abilities and critical thinking, which are increasingly being identified as necessary components of future education Critical thinking of students and teachers, as well as pedagogical methods can go beyond academic disciplines and are also central elements of sustainable education [7]. While these initiatives are a great start to explore these four areas of knowledge, they lack such an important process as creativity and innovation. Students enrolled in STEM programs may have more opportunities for hands-on learning, but they are limited to science, technology, engineering and mathematics. Our economy requires much more than an understanding of these areas - it requires application, creativity

[8].The introduction of the STEAM education system into the academic program of preschool education contributes to the formation of scientific prerequisites for thinking in children, which will arouse interest in professions in the scientific and technical sphere. Science, in turn, is the key to achieving technological progress in all spheres of activity [9]. Preparation for these rather complex professions requires great mental resources, knowledge and skills in various fields of science, the formation of which requires a lot of time and a special pedagogical approach. Therefore, there is an understanding among scientists that it is advisable to start preparing for this activity at an earlier age, namely in preschool, which is due to the susceptibility of children to new information and their great mental and physical potential. It is at preschool age that there is an intensive development of sensations, perception, memory, imagination, attention and speech. Through sensations and perception, the child learns the world in all its diversity of colors, sounds, smells, tastes and forms. A child involuntarily remembers a large amount of information, especially if this information is transmitted through vivid images, an interesting and emotionally intense educational process. By the end of preschool age, the manifestation of arbitrary memory begins. The intensive development of this type of memory is facilitated by gaming activities, especially role-playing, plot-role-playing games. In this regard, STEAM education has recently been widely introduced into the preschool education system in many countries of the world, intensively developing and implementing high technologies. Therefore, we consider it necessary to study the foreign experience of introducing STEAM education in the preschool sphere, training and advanced training of personnel for these purposes. The governments of countries, including Uzbekistan, are taking measures at the legislative level to educate and educate preschool children. Thus, by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 8, 2019, the Concept of development of the preschool education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 was approved, which provides for "creating conditions for the comprehensive intellectual, moral, aesthetic and physical development of

preschool children; ... introduction of innovations, advanced pedagogical and information and communication technologies into the preschool education system" The document was adopted due to the fact that over the past 20 years the number of preschool educational institutions has decreased by more than 45%, a number of systemic problems and shortcomings remain that hinder the successful implementation of state policy in the field of preschool education development: the lack of qualified teaching staff in preschool educational institutions; shortage and low level of qualification of managerial personnel in the system of preschool education; lack of modern teaching materials; lack of modern teaching aids; lack of modern teaching materials. Such a statement of tasks is due to the fact that currently educational technologies used in the preschool education system do not meet the challenges of a rapidly changing society, intensive development of computer technologies and the Internet, which radically change life at all levels of its existence. While rapid changes in technology pose additional problems in the field of professional development of teachers and the integration of these innovative technologies into the educational process, the existing higher education institutions of the country do not contribute to the formation of critical and creative engineering thinking for the following reasons: - insufficient attention is paid to the development of constructive thinking at all levels of education; - low level of development of creative thinking and imagination, the foundations of which are laid in the process of forming the basic culture of the individual in preschool age; - inability to work in a team and lack of leadership qualities and skills; - lack of respect for intellectual property. Thus, the In the Educational Program of Ministry of Pre-school and School Education of Republic (22.08.2022) subject "STEAM technologies in preschool education" was introduced into the Training courses for 2-3 courses of the specialty "Preschool education" , but without any connection with such subjects organically related to STEAM education as "Methods of forming elementary mathematical representations", "Methods of familiarization with nature", "Social communication of children", "Teaching

dramatizations and creative activity", "Methods of musical education", "Methods of teaching fine arts" and they are taught without including STEAM logic in the content of classes. We recommend creating a training module "STEAM technologies in preschool education", which includes such training courses as "Neuropsychology of a preschooler in STEAM training", "STEAM training-education of the future - Robotics for a preschooler", "STEAM training - environment and fundamentals of natural science for a preschooler", "STEAM - fundamentals of mathematics and physicists- for preschool education", "Teaching the basics of dramatization , creative activity and music education for preschoolers with STEAM training". Of course, the development and support of teachers with STEAM training is extremely important, since it is necessary to show how to use technology in their practice, and to strengthen their initial integration into it, constant support is needed since the teacher does not have time and motivation to use technology in teaching.

The introduction of the STEAM education system into the curriculum of preschool education contributes to the formation of scientific prerequisites for thinking in children, which will arouse interest in professions in the scientific and technical sphere. Science, in turn, is the key to technological progress in all spheres of activity. In countries where STEAM is integrated into the state educational program, you can see application developers - young and talented people from all over the world

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